

Access Genomed4All Data – Multiple Myeloma (MM)

The aim of this questionnaire is to assess whether the data which is owned by the Genomed4All consortium can be shared with the requester. It asks several questions on the purpose and the use which will be given to the data, and would then continue to state several conditions of use. The conditions of use need to be adhered to if data is to be shared.

Complete the form, then send it to Carolina Terragna - carolina.terragna@unibo.it

1. Name & Surname of the requester: _____

2. Email: _____

3. Company / Institution: _____

4. ORCID of Principal Investigator: _____

5. Describe the aim of the project for which the data will be used (and – if available – please attach to this request a document with a complete description of the project.

6. Describe the reason why the use of this data is important for the development of your project:

7. Given the data confidentiality and sensitivity, how do you plan to publish any results obtained from it?

8. Is this dataset the only source of information for your project? If not, please describe the other sources of data and how you plan to integrate them:

9. Provide a list of features you are interested in obtaining from the dataset

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|---|-------|----------|
| 10. Agree to use the requested data only for the registered research or study: | Agree | Disagree |
| 11. Agree to submit a new research project request if you intend to use the data for another purpose: | Agree | Disagree |
| 12. Agree that the datasets will not be shared with other researchers without the written consent of Genomed4All: | Agree | Disagree |
| 13. Agree to keep the data in a secure location where they cannot be accessed by unauthorized users: | Agree | Disagree |
| 14. Agree to take full responsibility for any data leak or data breach if occurred where the data is located on your secure location: | Agree | Disagree |
| 15. Agree to treat all data as confidential, and to make no effort to identify any individual, household or enumeration area in the survey: | Agree | Disagree |
| 16. Agree that no results will be published in which communities or individuals can be identified: | Agree | Disagree |
| 17. Agree that the data will not be used for any marketing or commercial venture: | Agree | Disagree |

Date _____

Signature _____